

Secundus Negrea-Muraru consecutive prime numbers relation, and adjacent Secundus Negrea-Muraru Conjecture

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Summary

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§ Section 2 (Research – Application of consideration; encompassing results; observations)

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§ Section 1 (Consideration and novel symbol reminder)

I. Consideration

Consider the sequence of all positive prime numbers:

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, ... ∞

Let a, b, c be consecutive prime numbers, $a < b < c$ such that:

$$a \quad \underline{\quad} \quad c$$

$$\frac{b}{c} + \frac{b}{a} = R(a,b,c) = R$$

II. Novel Symbol Reminder

For future representative and structural purposes, a quantitative symbol is to be established.

Proposed symbol:

- $\equiv$

Definition:

- the symbol $\equiv$ represents the remaining results or values of a properly delimited group, arrangement or series encompassing all results or values of said group, arrangement or series.

Usage:

- it is used to mention, observe or present a relation between one or more extracted results or values of a properly delimited group, arrangement or series encompassing all results or values of said group, arrangement or series, and all the other results or values of the properly delimited group, arrangement or series.

Example:

- Group A contains the elements {1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9}
- $\therefore$ by definition $1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5 < 6 < 7 < 8 < 9 \therefore 1 < \equiv$ elements of Group A
Therefore, consider the following symbol $\equiv$ to denote “all other”.

§ Section 2 (Research – Application of consideration; encompassing results; observations)

I. Application of consideration

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, ... ∞

a, b, c are consecutive p numbers $a < b < c$

a c

$$\frac{b}{c} + \frac{b}{a} = R_{(a,b,c)} = R$$

$$\frac{2}{5} + \frac{2}{3}$$

$$\frac{3}{5} + \frac{3}{2} = R_{(2,3,5)} = 0.9(6)$$

$$\frac{5}{3} + \frac{5}{7}$$

$$\frac{5}{7} + \frac{5}{3} = R_{(3,5,7)} = 0.5523809524 \dots$$

$$7 \quad 3$$

II. Encompassing Results

$$R_{(5,7,11)} = 0.379(220779)$$

$$R_{(7,11,13)} = 0.2(177822)$$

$$R_{(11,13,17)} = 0.1686548745372274784039489 \dots$$

$$R_{(13,17,19)} = 0.1262205286973088830673969 \dots$$

$$R_{(17,19,23)} = 0.1101090321712208911024363 \dots$$

$$R_{(19,23,29)} = 0.0948473131855125069044424 \dots$$

$$R_{(23,29,31)} = 0.0720607438216375683126177 \dots$$

$$R_{(29,31,37)} = 0.0664401887983645491988094 \dots \quad R_{(31,37,41)}$$

$$= 0.0561804920577540561804920 \dots$$

$$R_{(37,41,43)} = 0.0493323726449080958440004 \dots$$

$$R_{(41,43,47)} = 0.0469460904406174195339181 \dots$$

$$R_{(43,47,53)} = 0.0434867849840822309150149 \dots$$

$$R_{(47,53,59)} = 0.0387156475175036912546182 \dots$$

$$R_{(53,59,61)} = 0.0342338280549628565586876 \dots$$

$$R_{(59,61,67)} = 0.0330522989387599374618985 \dots$$

- 3-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(577,587,593)} = 0.003408429618050384611522 \dots$$

- 4-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(2857,2861,2879)} = 0.0006990768412502962030822 \dots$$

- 5-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(44189,44201,44203)} = 0.0000452478473415467888134 \dots$$

- 6-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(302551,302563,302567)} = 0.0000066101935887617855788 \dots$$

- 7-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(9821129,9821131,9821137)} = 0.0000002036425336349411817 \dots$$

- 8-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(22965073,22965127,22965133)} = 0.0000000870885669392042112 \dots$$

- 9-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(836131729,336131753,836131781)} = 0.0000000023919675252424049 \dots$$

- 10-digits consecutive p

$$R_{(8453501467,8453501477,8453501503)} = 0.0000000002365883540023660 \dots$$

III. Observations

- $0 < R_{(a,b,c)} < 1$
- the higher the consecutive primes that undergo the formulaic consideration are, the closer R is to 0.
- $R_{(2,3,5)}$ seems to give the highest value, i.e., 0.9(6).

§ Section 3 (Algebraic Method – Direct proof of interval of R)

I. Proof of minimum value of R $a <$

$$b < c$$

$$\frac{a}{c} + \frac{a}{b} \text{ through amplification} = \frac{a}{c} + \frac{a}{b} = \frac{a}{ac} + \frac{a}{bc} = \frac{a^2 + c^2}{abc}$$

$$= \frac{a^2 + c^2}{abc} > 0 \because a, b, c > 0 \quad \text{A}$$

II. Interval of R

$\therefore$ (I.) $\Rightarrow R \in (0, y)$, where y is to be proven.

§ Section 4 (Conjecture)

I.

From the conducted research, we assume the following:

$$R(2,3,5) > R(a,b,c)$$

References note:

Original work